

Flow Shop Scheduling Problem in Neutrosophic Environment Using Trapezoidal Fuzzy Numbers

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Abstract: In this paper, we propose to solve the flow shop scheduling problem using Branch and Bound method. This paper presents an algorithm with the help of branch and bound approach for a flow shop scheduling problems consisting of 4 jobs and 4 machines in which the processing time as Neutrosophic trapezoidal fuzzy numbers which are further converted in to crisp value using graded mean ranking method. Numerical example is given to illustrate the study of solving flow shop scheduling under Neutrosophic trapezoidal fuzzy number using branch and bound technique.

Keywords: Neutrosophic Fuzzy Set, Trapezoidal Fuzzy Number, Neutrosophic Trapezoidal Fuzzy Number, Flow shop scheduling Problem.

INTRODUCTION

Scheduling problems are common Occurrence in our real life. e.g. Programs to be run is a sequence at a computer centre, ordering of jobs for processing in a manufacturing plant. etc. The scheduling problem practically depends upon the important factors namely, transportation time, break down effect, etc. Flow shop scheduling is one of the most important decision making concept to arrange the task that is to be performed (or) processed in a machine in that particular order.

A geometrical model and a graphical algorithm for a sequencing problem were advanced by William. W. Hardgrave and George L.Nemhauser in 1963. These include a geometric approach a “Branch and Bound” approach, a combinatorial analysis approach, and an approximation approach.

This technique was developed by Little, et.al. All possible jobs are placed into the first sequence position and lower bounds on total time are calculated. In 1965, Zadeh [9] introduced the idea of fuzzy sets which gives best solution for impreciseness or vagueness. In 1986, K. Atanassov developed the concept of Intuitionistic Fuzzy Set (IFS) which is characterized by the membership degree and the non-membership degree.

In 1995, The new tool which is an Neutrosophic set theory was defined by Smarandache[7],to handle problems involving incomplete, indeterminate and inconsistent information, that cannot be solved with fuzzysset and Intuitionistic fuzzysset, Neutrosophic fuzzy set plays animportant role in handling imprecise condition.

In this paper, flow shop scheduling problems has been solved under Neutrosophic fuzzy environment. Here processing time is being taken in Neutrosophic trapezoidal fuzzy numbers and with the idea of Branch and bound technique we get the optimal solution to calculate total elapsed time.Numerical example is given to illustrate the study of solving flow shop scheduling under Neutrosophic trapezoidal fuzzy number using branch and bound technique

PRELIMINARIES

Definition

A **fuzzy set** \tilde{A} is defined by $\tilde{A} = \{(x, \mu_{\tilde{A}}(x)): x \in A\}$. In the pair $(x, \mu_{\tilde{A}}(x))$, the first element belong to the classical set A, the second element $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x)$, belong to the interval $[0, 1]$ is called the membership function.

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Definition

An **Intuitionist fuzzy set** \tilde{A}^I is defined by $\tilde{A}^I = \{ \langle \{x, \mu_{\tilde{A}^I}(x), \nu_{\tilde{A}^I}(x)\} \rangle / x \in X \}$, where $\mu_{\tilde{A}^I}(x), \nu_{\tilde{A}^I}(x): X \rightarrow [0,1]$ are function such that $0 \leq \mu_{\tilde{A}^I}(x) + \nu_{\tilde{A}^I}(x) \leq 1$ for all $x \in X$. Here $\mu_{\tilde{A}^I}(x)$ represented as the degree of membership and $\nu_{\tilde{A}^I}(x)$ represented as the degree of non-membership of the element.

Definition

A **Neutrosophic fuzzy set** \tilde{A}^N is defined as $\tilde{A}^N = \{ \langle x, T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x) \rangle : x \in X \}$ where $T_A(x), I_A(x), F_A(x): X \rightarrow [0,1]$ and $0 \leq T_A(x) + I_A(x) + F_A(x) \leq 3$ where $T_A(x)$ is membership, $I_A(x)$ is indeterministic function and $F_A(x)$ is non-deterministic function.

Definition

Fuzzy number \tilde{A} is a fuzzy set on the real line \mathfrak{R} , must satisfy the following conditions.

- (i) $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x_0)$ is piecewise continuous
- (ii) There exist atleast one $x_0 \in \mathfrak{R}$ with $\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x_0) = 1$
- (iii) \tilde{A} must be normal & convex.

Triangular Fuzzy Number

A fuzzy number $\tilde{A} = (a_1, a_2, a_3)$ is said to be triangular fuzzy number if its membership function is given by,

$$\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} 0 & \text{for } x < a_1 \\ \frac{(x - a_1)}{(a_2 - a_1)} & \text{for } a_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ \frac{(a_3 - x)}{(a_3 - a_2)} & \text{for } a_2 \leq x \leq a_3 \\ 0 & \text{for } x > a_3 \end{cases}$$

where $a_1 \leq a_2 \leq a_3$ are real numbers.

Trapezoidal Fuzzy Number

A fuzzy number $\tilde{A} = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4)$ is said to be trapezoidal fuzzy number if its membership function is given by,

$$\mu_{\tilde{A}}(x) = \begin{cases} 0, & x < a_1 \\ \frac{x - a_1}{a_2 - a_1}, & a_1 \leq x \leq a_2 \\ 1, & a_2 \leq x \leq a_3 \\ \frac{a_4 - x}{a_4 - a_3}, & a_3 \leq x \leq a_4 \\ 0, & x > a_4 \end{cases}$$

where $a_1 \leq a_2 \leq a_3 \leq a_4$ are real numbers.

Definition

A **Neutrosophic trapezoidal fuzzy set** \tilde{A}^N in U is represented by

$$\tilde{A}^N = \{ \langle x: \bar{T}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x), \bar{I}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x), \bar{F}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x) \rangle ; x \in U \}$$

$\bar{T}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x), \bar{I}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x), \bar{F}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x): U \rightarrow M[0,1]$, where

$\bar{T}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x)$ denote the truth membership value,

$\bar{I}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x)$ denote the indeterminacy value and

$\bar{F}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x)$ denote the falsity-membership value of x in \tilde{A}^N and for every $x \in U$.

Here $\bar{T}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x) = (T_{\tilde{A}^N}^1(x), T_{\tilde{A}^N}^2(x), T_{\tilde{A}^N}^3(x), T_{\tilde{A}^N}^4(x))$; $\bar{I}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x) = (I_{\tilde{A}^N}^1(x), I_{\tilde{A}^N}^2(x), I_{\tilde{A}^N}^3(x), I_{\tilde{A}^N}^4(x))$

$$\bar{F}_{\tilde{A}^N}(x) = (F_{\tilde{A}^N}^1(x), F_{\tilde{A}^N}^2(x), F_{\tilde{A}^N}^3(x), F_{\tilde{A}^N}^4(x))$$

RANKING FUNCTION OF TRAPEZOIDAL FUZZY NUMBER

An efficient approach for comparing the fuzzy number is by the use of a ranking function based on their graded means.

That is for every $\tilde{A} = (a_1, a_2, a_3, a_4) \in F(R)$, the ranking function $R: F(R) \rightarrow R$ by graded means is defined a function.

$$R(\tilde{A}) = \frac{(a_1 + 2a_2 + 2a_3 + a_4)}{6}$$

BRANCH AND BOUND ALGORITHM

Branch and Bound is an algorithm design paradigm which is generally used for combinatorial optimization problems. It is a solution approach that can be applied to a number of different types of problems. This method uses a tree diagram of nodes and branches to organize the solution partitioning, it represent subsets of the solution set, the branch is checked against lower estimated bounds of the optimal solution. It maintain provable lower bounds in global objective value.

Here let k be the level number in the branch tree and ϵ be the assignment in the current node of a branching tree. Assume root node be 0.

Let p_{ϵ}^k be the assignment at level k of the branching tree and v_{ϵ} be the lower bound of the partial assignment up to top_{ϵ}^k such that

$$v_{\epsilon} = \sum_{i \notin X} a_{i,j} + \sum_{k \in X} \sum_{j \in Y} \min a_{i,j}$$

Where $a_{i,j}$ is the processing time of the machine

NUMERICAL EXAMPLE

We Consider 4 jobs, 4 machine flow shop scheduling problem where processing time of the jobs are represented as Neutrosophic trapezoidal fuzzy numbers. Our objective is to obtain an optimal schedule and the total elapsed time. Using branch and bound technique.

Machines/ jobs	Machine A	Machine B	Machine C	Machine D
J_1	((9,12,15,21); (10,13,16,22); (15,18,21,27))	((0,1,2,6); (1,4,7,7); (9,12,15,21))	((7,8,9,13); (5,10,15,17); (13,16,19,25))	((16,19,22,28); (14,20,26,32); (18,21,24,30))
J_2	((1,4,7,7); (12,15,18,24); (14,17,20,32))	((2,5,8,14); (3,6,9,15); (8,11,14,14))	((0,1,2,6); (1,4,7,7); (9,12,15,21))	((10,13,16,22); (16,19,22,22); (19,22,25,31))
J_3	((7,10,13,19); (9,12,15,21); (13,16,19,19))	((2,3,4,8); (4,6,8,10); (8,11,14,20))	((1,2,3,7); (5,6,11,15); (14,20,26,32))	((10,13,16,22); (20,23,26,32); (21,24,27,33))
J_4	((3,6,9,19); (4,7,10,16); (24,27,30,36))	((3,5,7,9); (5,10,15,17); (11,13,19,21))	((7,8,9,13); (8,11,14,14); (11,13,19,21))	((22,25,28,34); (25,28,31,37); (29,32,35,41))

Step (1) converting the processing time of above Neutrosophic trapezoidal fuzzy number in to Neutrosophic number using graded mean ranking method.

Machines/ jobs	Machine A	Machine B	Machine C	Machine D
J_1	(14,15,20)	(2,5,14)	(9,12,18)	(21,23,23)
J_2	(15,17,20)	(7,8,12)	(2,5,14)	(15,20,34)
J_3	(12,14,17)	(4,7,13)	(3,9,23)	(15,25,26)
J_4	(7,9,29)	(6,12,16)	(9,12,16)	(27,30,34)

Step (2) Apply branch and bound method Compute the lower bound p_{11}^1

$$v_{\epsilon} = \sum_{i \notin X} a_{i,j} + \sum_{k \in X} \sum_{j \in Y} \min a_{i,j}$$

Where $\epsilon = (1,1)$, $X = (2,3,4)$ and $Y = (2,3,4)$

$$v_{11} = a_{11} + \sum_{X \in \{2,3,4\}} \sum_{Y \in \{2,3,4\}} \min a_{i,j}$$

$$p_{11}^1 = (14,15,20) + (2,5,14) + (4,7,13) + (6,12,16) = (26,39,63)$$

$$p_{21}^1 = (5,17,20) + (2,5,14) + (4,7,13) + (6,12,16) = (17,41,63)$$

$$p_{31}^1 = (12,14,17) + (2,5,14) + (2,5,14) + (6,12,16) = (22,36,61)$$

$$p_{41}^1 = (7,9,29) + (2,5,14) + (2,5,14) + (4,7,13) = (15,26,70)$$

Further branching: Further branching is done from the terminal node which has the least lower bound .At this stage; the nodes $p_{11}^1, p_{21}^1, p_{31}^1, p_{41}^1$ are the terminal nodes .The node p_{41}^1 has the least lower bound. Hence, further branching is started from the node

Here p_{41}^1 is minimum therefore eliminate fourth row and first column further branching is starting from this node .

$$v_{22} = a_{41} + a_{i2} + \sum_{X \in \{3,4\}} \sum_{Y \in \{3,4\}} \min a_{i,j}$$

$$p_{12}^2 = (7,9,29) + (2,5,14) + (2,5,14) + (3,9,23) = (14,28,80)$$

$$p_{22}^2 = (7,9,29) + (7,8,12) + (9,12,18) + (3,9,23) = (26,38,82)$$

$$p_{32}^2 = (7,9,29) + (4,7,13) + (9,12,18) + (2,5,14) = (22,33,74)$$

Here p_{12}^2 is minimum and therefore eliminate first row and second column

Further branching is starting from this node

$$v_{33} = a_{41} + a_{i2} + a_{i3} + \sum_{X \in \{4\}} \sum_{Y \in \{4\}} \min a_{i,j}$$

$$p_{23}^3 = (7, 9,29) + (2,5,14) + (2,5,14) + (15,25,26) = (26,44,83)$$

$$p_{33}^3 = (7,9,29) + (2,5,14) + (3,9,23) + (15,20,24) = (27,43,90)$$

Here p_{23}^3 is minimum and eliminate third row and third column. Therefore remaining a_{ij} is in p_{34}^4 . We get the sequence as

From the lower bounds, we can determine that the optimal sequence will be taken as 4-1-2-3

Step (3) Total elapsed time

Machines/ jobs	Machine A		Machine B		Machine C		Machine D	
	In	Out	In	Out	In	Out	In	Out
J ₄	-	(7,9,29)	(7,9,29)	(13,21,45)	(13,21,45)	(22,33,61)	(22,33,61)	(49,63,95)
J ₁	(7,9,29)	(21,24,49)	(21,24,49)	(23,29,63)	(23,29,63)	(32,41,81)	(49,63,95)	(70,86,118)
J ₂	(21,24,49)	(36,41,69)	(36,41,69)	(43,49,81)	(43,49,81)	(45,54,95)	(70,86,118)	(85,106,152)
J ₃	(36,41,69)	(48,55,86)	(48,55,86)	(52,62,99)	(52,62,99)	(55,71,122)	(85,106,152)	(100,131,178)

Neutrosophic fuzzy total elapsed time= **(100,131,178) Hours**

CONCLUSION

We proposed the flow shop scheduling problem in Neutrosophic fuzzy environment is solved by branch and bound method after defuzzification, which is easy to understand. It helps to formulate uncertainty for the decision makers in real life situation.

REFERENCES

- [1] Ambika, G., & Uthra, G. (2014). Branch and Bound Technique in flow shop scheduling using fuzzy processing times. *Annals of Pure and Applied Mathematics*, 8(2), 37-42.
- [2] Brown, A. P. G., & Lomnicki, Z. A. (1966). Some applications of the "branch-and-bound" algorithm to the machine scheduling problem. *Journal of the Operational Research Society*, 17(2), 173-186.
- [3] Gupta, D. (2011). Application of branch and bound technique for nx 3 flow shop scheduling in which processing time associated with their respective probabilities. *Mathematical Modeling and Theory*, 2(1), 31-36.
- [4] Ignall, E., & Schrage, L. (1965). Application of the branch and bound technique to some flow-shop scheduling problems. *Operations research*, 13(3), 400-412.
- [5] Temiz, İ., & Erol, S. (2004). Fuzzy branch-and-bound algorithm for flow shop scheduling. *Journal of intelligent manufacturing*, 15(4), 449-454.
- [6] Petrovic, S., & Song, X. (2006). A new approach to two-machine flow shop problem with uncertain processing times. *Optimization and Engineering*, 7(3), 329-342.
- [7] Broumi, S., Bakali, A., Talea, M., Smarandache, F., & Vladareanu, L. (2016). Shortest path problem under triangular fuzzy neutrosophic information. *10th International Conference on Software, Knowledge, Information Management & Applications (SKIMA)*, 169-174.
- [8] Santhi, S. and Selvakumari, K. (2016). Flow shop scheduling problem under branch and bound method in neutrosophic environment.
- [9] Thangavelu, K., Uthra, G., & Shunmugapriya, S. (2016). Optimal Solution of Three Stage Fuzzy flow Shop Scheduling Problem Using Branch and Bound Technique. *Global Journal of Pure and Applied Mathematics (GJPAM)*, 12(1).
- [10] Zadeh, L.A. (1965). Fuzzy sets information and computation 8, 338-353.